

Derivatives of Antimony(III) with Glycols

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Reactions of ethyl antimonite with a number of glycols have been studied in different stoichiometric ratios in presence of benzene. The products of reaction in equimolar proportion, disproportionated into the relatively stable bis-antimony triglycolates, except those with hexylene glycol and pinacol which distill and sublime respectively. The analyses of the products correspond to the diglycolates, both when the ethyl antimonite and the glycols are taken in 1:2 or 1:3 molar ratios. On being heated under reduced pressure, these derivatives disproportionate into the bis-antimony triglycolates with the release of a mole of glycol per three moles of the compounds. The bis-antimony triglycolates have also been prepared with ethylene and propylene glycols and pinacol.

Several glycol derivatives of aluminium¹, boron², titanium³, germanium⁴, zirconium⁵, silicon⁶, niobium, and tantalum⁷ have been studied in detail in our laboratories.

The bis-antimony triglycolate⁸ is reported to have been prepared by boiling antimony trioxide with ethylene glycol and crystallising the product in excess glycol. This compound has been reported to act as a catalyst⁹ in poly-condensation processes.

The mono-ethoxy⁹ derivatives of propylene glycol and butane-1,3-diol (viz. cyclo-1-methylethylenedioxyethoxystibine and cyclo-1-methyltrimethylenedioxyethoxystibine) have also been prepared by the action of sodium ethoxide on the corresponding monochloroantimonite derivatives. In the second case, the amount of the compound isolated was too meagre for analysis.

In view of these observations and the possible applications of such compounds as antioxidants¹⁰ and as catalysts in the manufacture of artificial fibres⁹, it was considered worthwhile to apply the technique of glycolysis to the preparation of similar antimony derivatives.

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The reactions of ethyl antimonite and various glycols in different stoichiometric ratios, carried out during the present investigation, can be represented as:

(where R = ethylene, propylene, trimethylene, tetramethylene, 1,2-dimethylethylene, 1-methyltrimethylene, 1,3,3-trimethyltrimethylene, and tetramethylethylene)

(where R = ethylene, propylene, tetramethylethylene).

With propylene and hexylene glycols, the reactions were also carried out in 1:3 molar ratio. But on washing the products with a small amount of benzene, the diglycollates were obtained as the final end products.

All the derivatives (1:1, 1:2, and 2:3) obtained with hexylene and propylene glycols as well as with butane-1,3 and -1,4-diols are soluble in boiling benzene; the rest of the products are either insoluble or sparingly soluble.

The products of the reaction in 1:1 ratio, except with hexylene glycol, which distilled at 106°/3.5 mm, and with pinacol, which sublimed, disproportionated on heating.

All the diglycollates disproportionated on heating to the relatively stable bis-antimony triglycollate with the release of a mole of glycol.

TABLE I

Reactions of ethyl antimonite with glycols.

No.	Reactants.	Formula.	%Antimony. EtOH in As (moles).		Action of heat.	Remarks.	
			Found.	Reqd. Found.			
I. In molar ratio 1:1.							
1.	EA (2.81 g.) + propylene glycol (1.19 g.)	$C_3H_8O_4.Sb.OEt$	50.18	50.57	1.79	2	Antimony triethoxide di- & bis-ant. triprop. glycolate sublimes at 160°/3.5 mm.
2.	EA (2.425 g.) + butane-1,3 diol (0.861 g.)	$C_4H_{10}O_4.Sb.OEt$	47.56	47.79	1.87	2	Di- & bis-ant. triprop. glycolate sublimes at 160°/3.5 mm.
3.	EA (1.485 g.) + butane-2,3-diol (0.5 g.)	$C_4H_{10}O_4.Sb.OEt$	48.37	47.79	1.902	2	Ethoxide diethyl & white needles subl. at 90°/0.6 mm (bis-ant. triglycolate)
4.	EA (2.99 g.) + butane-1,4-diol (1.05 g.)	$C_4H_{10}O_4.Sb.OEt$	47.99	47.79	1.89	2	Ethoxide diethyl & bis-ant. triglycolate sublimes
5.	EA (4.89 g.) + trimethylene glycol (1.448 g.)	$C_3H_8O_4.SB.OEt$	50.59	50.37	1.99	2	Ethoxide diethyl, bis-ant. triglycolate remains as residuum benzene.
6.	EA (3.74 g.) + hexylene glycol (1.72 g.)	$C_6H_{14}O_6.Sb.OEt$	43.05	43.06	1.99	2	Diethyl at 106°/3.5 mm. Found Sb, 43.1%
7.	EA (3.18 g.) + pinacol (1.46 g.)	$C_6H_{14}O_6.Sb.OEt$	43.42	43.06	1.87	2	Sublimes at 160°/7 mm. Found Sb, 43.75% in benzene.

N. B. EA. denotes ethyl antimonite.

TABLE I (contd.)

No.	Reactants.	Formula.	%Antimony.		Alcohol in A. (moles)	Action of heat.	Remarks.
			Found.	Reqd.			
B. In molar ratio 1:2.							
8.	EA (1.98 g.) + propylene glycol (1.17 g.)	$C_3H_6O_2 \cdot Sb \cdot OP_r$	45.15	44.97	2.93	3	Disprop. into bis-ant. triglyc. (Found Sb, 52.6; calc. 52.31) & propylene glycol
9.	EA (5.28 g.) + butane-1,3-diol (3.69 g.)	$C_4H_8O_2 \cdot Sb \cdot OC_2H_4OH$	40.47	40.75	2.935	3	Disprop. into bis-ant. triglyc. (Found Sb, 48.16; calc. 47.98)
10.	EA (2.015 g.) + butane-1,4-diol (1.41 g.)	$C_4H_8O_2 \cdot Sb \cdot OC_2H_4OH$	41.05	40.75	2.91	3	Disprop.
11.	EA (2.14 g.) + butane-2,3-diol (1.5 g.)	$C_4H_8O_2 \cdot Sb \cdot OC_2H_4OH$	40.41	40.75	2.90	3	Disprop.
12.	EA (3.72 g.) + trimethylene glycol (2.2 g.)	$C_3H_6O_2 \cdot Sb \cdot OC_2H_4OH$	45.50	44.57	2.82	3	Trimethylene glycol diastis & residue contains 53.48% Sb; bis-ant. triglyc. req. 52.28%
13.	EA (2.45 g.) + hexylene glycol (2.25 g.)	$C_6H_{12}O_2 \cdot Sb \cdot OC_2H_4OH$	33.95	34.32	2.77	3	Hexylene glycol diastis; white solid sublimes (Sb, 41.39; calc. 41.25%)
14.	EA (3.24 g.) + pinacol (2.98 g.)	$C_6H_{12}O_2 \cdot Sb \cdot OC_2H_4OH$	34.57	34.32	2.90	3	Subl. (Sb, 41.55% at 135°/2.5 mm and pinacol diastis)
C. In molar ratio 2:3.							
15.	EA (2.74 g.) + propylene glycol (1.31 g.)	$Sb_2(C_3H_6O)_3$	52.23	52.31	5.55	6	Sublimes at 160°/2.5 mm benzene.
16.	EA (4.06 g.) + pinacol (2.8 g.)	$Sb_2(C_6H_{12}O)_3$	41.39	42.25	8.47	6	Do at 139°/2.5 mm benzene. White solid, insoluble in benzene.

EXPERIMENTAL

All-glass apparatus fitted with interchangeable joints was used throughout and special precautions were taken to exclude moisture. All the fractionations were carried out in a fractionating column, packed with Raschig rings and fitted to a total condensation variable take-off still-head.

Benzene (B.D.H.) was refluxed over metallic sodium, distilled, and finally dried azeotropically with ethanol. The glycols were purified by distillation.

Ethyl antimonite was prepared by the action of sodium ethoxide (3 *M*) on antimony trichloride (1 *M*) in a large excess of benzene. The precipitated sodium chloride was filtered and the excess solvent distilled slowly in a fractionating column. The final product was distilled at 89°/5mm. [Found: Sb, 48.7; OEt, 51.5. Sb (OEt)₃ requires Sb, 47.42; (CH₃O)₃OEt, 52.58%].

Antimony was estimated volumetrically¹⁷ with 0.1 *N* potassium bromate solution, using methyl red as indicator. The ethanol in the azeotrope was estimated by chromic acid oxidation method¹⁸.

Reaction of Ethyl Antimonite and Ethylene Glycol

In 1:1 molar ratio.—A slight heat was evolved and a white precipitate began to form when ethylene glycol (1.012 g.) was added to ethyl antimonite (4.147 g.) in benzene (50 ml). The contents were refluxed at 110–15° for about 2 hr. and the ethanol liberated in the reaction was slowly fractionated azeotropically. The excess solvent was distilled under reduced pressure when a white solid was obtained (3.41 g., 93.2%). [Found: Sb, 53.8. (CH₃O)₂Sb-OEt requires Sb, 53.7%]. Ethanol in azeotrope, 1.41 g. (2 moles require 1.48 g.).

The above compound on heating in a distillation assembly afforded a colorless fuming liquid which distilled at 55°/0.5 mm. (Found: Sb, 47.68. Calc. for ethoxide: Sb, 47.42%).

The white residue in the flask was found to contain 57.28% antimony (bis-antimony triethyleneglycollate requires Sb, 57.49%).

In 1:2 molar ratio.—Ethylene glycol (2.85 g.) was mixed with ethyl antimonite (5.88 g.) in benzene (40 ml). A white solid separated with evolution of heat. The contents were refluxed for about 3 hr. The ethanol liberated during the reaction was slowly fractionated azeotropically. The compound was finally dried by distilling excess benzene under reduced pressure. A white powder (5.15 g., 92.7%) was obtained. [Found: Sb, 49.74. (CH₃O)₂Sb(OCH₂CH₂OH) requires Sb, 50.15%]. Ethanol in azeotrope, 3.0 g. (3 moles require 3.15 g.).

This compound on heating in a distillation assembly provided a colorless, heavy liquid and a white solid residue. (Found: Sb, 57.08. Calc. for bis-antimony triethyleneglycollate: Sb, 57.49%).

In 2:3 molar ratio.—Ethylene glycol (1.825 g.) was added to ethyl antimonite (4.78 g.) in benzene (35 ml). A white solid separated. The contents were refluxed for about 2½ hr.

and the ethanol liberated during the reaction was fractionated azeotropically. The excess benzene was distilled under reduced pressure. A white powder (4.1 g.) was obtained. The compound was unaffected by heat up to 100°/0.5 mm. [Found: Sb, 57.66. Calc. for bis-antimony triethyleneglycollate: Sb, 57.49%]. Ethanol in azeotrope, 2.52 g. (6 moles require 2.56 g).

For brevity, other reactions are summarised in Table I.

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